

FALLING-WEIGHT IMPACT AND POST-IMPACT FLEXURAL PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID FLAX/CARBON LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid laminates produced using carbon (C) and flax (F) fiber pre-pregs with epoxy resin were fabricated, with two different stacking sequences, in general terms based on the presence of flax fiber laminates as outer layers and carbon as inner layers (FCF) or vice versa. Pure flax and pure carbon fiber reinforced laminates were also fabricated for comparison. Experimental tests were performed, which included four-point bending, falling weight impact tests at energies ranging from 5 to 30 Joules with determination of the BVID and post-impact flexural tests. In general terms, CFC proved slightly superior to FCF as for flexural performance, although on the other side the presence of flax laminates on the outside guaranteed a higher impact damage tolerance, acting as hindrances to crack propagation in the laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Information on falling weight impact (IFW) performance of composites including plant fibers, such as jute, flax, hemp, sisal, etc., appears still quite limited, despite the fact that IFW represents an important way of assessing the suitability of these materials to a possible structural use. In this regard, hybridisation may increase the flexibility of composite materials, also in terms of impact performance [1]. In the specific case of plant fibers, hybridization represents a significant strategy to reduce on one side weight and carbon footprint of composite materials, whilst retaining a sufficient mechanical

performance to permit non purely cosmetic applications [2]. Hybrids including plant fibers were fabricated most frequently with glass fiber composites, less so with carbon fiber ones: one of the few recent examples using flax and carbon fibers is in [3]. The reason for that is that plant fiber composites have been primarily intended for replacement of fiberglass, whereas they bear obvious limitations in terms of strength, stiffness and variability of properties to be able to possibly compete with carbon fiber composites. However, also carbon/plant fiber hybrid composites may have some role especially for the possible combination of properties, since plant fiber composites might allow different modes of damage propagation and dissipation and possibly even have some effect on the inherent brittleness of carbon fiber composites. Also they might be of interest in view of particular applications, where the importance of impact performance coupled with weight as low as possible is paramount. This can be of interest of the automotive sector, where e.g., carbon/sisal hybrid composites have been proposed [4], and potentially also of the aerospace interiors sector, where attention to plant fibers was scant so far. In this case, the insertion of some amount of plant fibers would improve the end-of-life scenario of the otherwise not recyclable thermosetting matrix composites.

In this respect, IFW can offer some information, especially of the possible relation between stacking sequence and damage tolerance. In particular, comparison have been carried out between composites reinforced with intercalated layers of plant and glass fibers and composites reinforced with glass fibers on the outer layers and plant fibers on the inner ones, or vice versa [5]. The outcome of previous works on glass/plant/basalt fiber hybrids as regards impact resistance and the assessment of the influence of stacking sequence on structural properties was promising, in terms of the possibility to tailor as much as possible the composite structure on the application requirements [6]. However, some issues remain open to discussion, in particular in the case of carbon/plant fibre composites, such as the influence of stacking sequence on the appearance of BVID and the reduction of performance with increasing impact energies. These are amongst the subjects investigated in this work.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two unidirectional prepreg material systems based on epoxy matrix (180 g/m² for flax and 300 g/m² for carbon) were supplied by Lineo and DeltaPreg S.p.A., respectively. Four different types of laminates were manufactured: all flax and all carbon laminates and two different hybrid laminates with sandwich configuration (flax skins with carbon core and vice versa). The details of the configurations are summarized in table 1.

Laminate	Stacking sequence	Number of flax layers	Number of carbon layers	Total fiber vol. fraction (%)
F	[0/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/0] _s	18	-	56 ± 0.1
C	[0/90/0/90/0/90/0] _s	-	14	59 ± 0.2
FCF	[0 ^F /0 ^F /90 ^F /90 ^F /0 ^C /0 ^C /90 ^C /90 ^C /0 ^C] _s	8	10	62 ± 0.1
CFC	[0 ^C /0 ^C /90 ^C /90 ^C /0 ^F /0 ^F /90 ^F /90 ^F /0 ^F] _s	10	8	60 ± 0.1

Table 1: Summary of the different configurations

For each system, ASTM D7136 standard panels were vacuum-bagged and fully cured under pressure in an autoclave oven to the manufacturer's specifications. Panels were cut to create test coupons measuring 100 × 150 mm to within the tolerances of ASTM D7136. For each material system, coupons were impacted at room temperature according to ASTM D7136 procedure at target impact energies from 5 to 30 J in order to find the BVID threshold. An instrumented drop-weight

impact testing machine (CEAST/Instron 9340) was used for this purpose equipped with a hemispherical tip (diameter of 16 mm). While BVID is subjective by nature, it is often defined as damage visible within a range of 1 m, or damage causing a specific permanent indentation. The depth of the residual indentation caused by BVID varies in the literature and in this study 0.3 mm of dent depth was chosen as the threshold of detectability (as commonly adopted by aeronautical standards). Post-impact, the dent depth of each coupon was measured using a contact profilometer (Taylor-Hobson Talyscan 150). Four-point bending tests have been performed on impacted and non-impacted specimens (150 × 25 × 4.5 mm) in accordance with ASTM D 6272 to determine the decay of flexural properties on a Zwick/Roell Z010 universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The distance between the loading noses (the load span) was one half of the support span (120 mm). A cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/min was used.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flexural strength results before impact, summarized in Table 2, indicate a substantially linear effect of the introduction of carbon fibers: therefore even the introduction of a slightly higher amount of carbon fibers, such as in CFC composites with respect to FCF, produces a perceivable increase of flexural strength though at a level compatible with the real difference in stacking sequence. In contrast, as regards flexural modulus CFC are largely superior to FCF, in practice the former is more than doubling the stiffness value of the latter. It can be suggested that after the introduction of a given amount of flax fibers, the behavior of the composite becomes quite abruptly more elasto-plastic than prevalently elastic. However, a good signal in terms of the quality of the composites obtained is that the standard deviation of flexural data is consistently kept at a very low level.

Laminate	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural stiffness (GPa)
F	183.6 ± 2.9	20.5 ± 0.4
C	1044.8 ± 31.7	82.5 ± 1.2
CFC	641.1 ± 1	74.8 ± 0.5
FCF	534.9 ± 12.5	36.2 ± 0.5

Table 2: Flexural strength and stiffness of the non-impacted laminates

In terms of impact damage, it can be noticed though from data reported in Figure 1 that, whilst C and FCF laminates only reach indentation levels suggesting BVID at the maximum energy applied, i.e. 30 Joules, CFC laminates reach it at 15 J already, whilst F laminates show BVID even at only 5 J. Maximum force measured during IFW tests confirm that no margin for improvement is offered by F laminates from 5 J above, whereas the other laminates basically show that maximum force steadily and consistently grows with impact energy (Table 3). Impact markedly reduced flexural strength for all laminates, as shown in Figure 2, even at the lowest impact energy applied, however, the effect appears more controllable in the case of FCF laminates, though in general terms they would start from lowest values than CFC laminates. As expected, flax fiber laminates are in themselves not able to withstand impacts at energy as high as 30 J, collapsing at an early stage at the application of a flexural stress. This is not the case for any of the hybrid laminates, and obviously not for carbon fiber reinforced ones. In contrast, flexural stiffness, whose evolution with impact energy is reported in Figure 3, is substantially preserved up to 20 J and in a large measure also at 30 J, with the lowest performance obtained in the case of CFC laminates.

It is noteworthy that most of the differences observed in terms of post-impact residual performance are most likely offered by the specific mode of impact damage encountered in the laminates, in particular at the higher energies applied. To try to initiate a possible investigation of this aspect, in

Figure 4 and Figure 5 a picture of damage revealed on the two surfaces of CFC and FCF laminates subjected to 30 J impact are reported, respectively. It can be observed that, whilst on CFC laminates the external layers are experimenting a diffuse elongated tearing, which contributes to crack propagation, on FCF the presence of flax fiber laminates as outer layers tends to constrain more damage in the impacted region.

The results can be effectively summarized saying that the requirements of flexural and impact testing appear to be rather different as regards the respective introduction of flax and carbon fiber: a very general consideration, though only qualitative, would suggest that having flax fiber laminates on the outer layers would be more beneficial for impact, where they might act in hindering linear cracks propagation, whilst the opposite would be through for flexural properties. An obvious limitation of this study needs to be mentioned though, in that the effect of different fabric structures (e.g., twill, satin) or different rotation of the layers during stacking (angle-ply) [3] would modify the outcome of these tests, which would be the rationale to further extend this study.

Max. force (N)	Impact energy (J)				
	Laminates	5	10	15	20
F	2005 ± 73	2133 ± 151	2473 ± 139	2549 ± 216	2387 ± 1
C	3830 ± 39	4713 ± 10	5615 ± 62	6223 ± 315	7423 ± 240
CFC	3190 ± 49	4619 ± 71	5407 ± 169	5808 ± 33	6883 ± 251
FCF	3161 ± 25	3980 ± 67	4777 ± 42	5431 ± 30	6738 ± 79

Table 3: Values of max force (N) vs. impact energy (J) on all the laminates during IFW tests

Figure 1: Indentation vs. Impact energy for the different laminates and determination of BVID

Figure 2: Normalized residual strength of the different laminates

Figure 3: Normalized residual stiffness of the different laminates

Figure 4: Impact damage for the highest impact energy (30 J) on a CFC laminate

Figure 5: Impact damage for the highest impact energy (30 J) on a FCF laminate

4 CONCLUSIONS

The introduction of flax fiber laminates to be stacked together with carbon fiber ones, so to produce a hybrid composite, apart from some projected environmental benefit at end-of-life, has also some other advantage. Whereas in static tests, such as flexural ones, the improvement in properties obtained by the addition of carbon fiber tends to be predictable, for dynamic tests, such as falling weight impact (IFW) tests both the value of energy for which barely visible impact damage (BVID) is detected and the residual static performance would depend also on the stacking sequence, more in particular on whether flax and carbon fiber laminates are used as outer or inner layers respectively. This suggests that the fabrication of mixed stacking sequences alternating in more complex ways flax and carbon fiber laminates could offer the advantage of having a hybrid composite with properties more tailored on requirements. This can be of interest of sectors such as automotive or aerospace, where plant fiber composites have found limited application so far.

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